

Rational choice or normative institutionalism? Problematizing UK universities' recruitment processes for globally mobile knowledge workers

Refereed Paper

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Abstract

Rational choice and resource dependence theories suggest that external resources are crucial to organizations. Organizations depending on globally mobile knowledge workers as a resource are assumed to choose rational processes for international recruitment. However, an empirical study of recruitment processes in UK universities indicates that this is not the case. This phenomenon is problematized and normative institutionalism offered as an alternative theoretical explanation. Implications are discussed for theory on recruitment processes in other contexts and practice in other industries. Normative institutionalism can have far-reaching societal impact: The industry examined aims to educate future global knowledge workers, and flawed theoretical assumptions may negatively influence the careers of many young people. A three-level moderator model of knowledge worker mobility and the metaphor 'currency' of career capital is offered to help integrate theories, clarify concepts, and provide a basis for further research.

Keywords

Normative institutionalism; recruitment; international; knowledge work; mobility; qualitative, problematization